

Microwave-induced synthesis of enantiopure beta lactams from L-glyceraldehyde

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Microwave-induced asymmetric synthesis of β -lactams from L-glyceraldehyde derived imines is achieved following a reaction with acid chlorides in the presence of a tertiary base. An exclusive formation of the *cis* enantiomer (3*S*,4*R*) is observed. The whole process is highly efficient and it completed within 2 h.

Keywords: L-Glyceraldehyde acetonide, β -lactam, cycloaddition, microwave.

Introduction

Research on β -lactams is one of the most important areas. Many β -lactams are used as antibiotics. However, other clinical and pre-clinical applications of β -lactams are also well established¹. Synthesis of optically active β -lactams with minimum number of steps and easy method are crucial because natural and non-natural products can be prepared from them. In this paper, a simple and fast method for the preparation of chiral β -lactams is described through microwave-induced reactions². In contrast to conventional method, microwave-assisted procedure is much more efficient in all respects. This method does not require any nitrogen atmosphere and dry conditions. The reaction is extremely rapid, the entire process is economical, work-up procedure is simple and all the reactions can be performed in an Erlenmeyer flask.

Results and discussion

L-Ascorbic acid lactone (**1**) was hydrogenated to the saturated diol **2** and it was then protected as ketal **3**. The product **3** was oxidized with aqueous sodium metaperiodate to the L-glyceraldehyde acetonide (**4**) following a known procedure (Scheme 1)³.

Reagents and conditions: (a) $\text{H}_2/\text{Pd-C}$, (b) isopropenylmethyl ether, DMF, 70%, (c) $\text{NaIO}_4/\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 80%.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of L-(*S*)-glyceraldehyde acetonide from L-ascorbic acid.

L-Glyceraldehyde acetonide **4** was treated with a few primary aromatic amines dissolved in dichloroethane (aniline, *p*-anisidine and *p*-methylaniline) to form imines **5a-c** (Scheme 2)⁴. The imines **5a-c** was dried thoroughly with anhydrous sodium sulfate.

Microwave irradiation of the imine solution in dichloroethane with acetoxyacetyl chloride, methoxyacetyl chloride and phenoxyacetyl chloride in the presence of *N*-methyl morpholine for a short period of time (approximately 2 min) afforded a single β -lactam **6** in 80–90% yield. Other enanti-

Entry	R ¹	R ²	Diastereomeric ratio		Time (min)	Yield (%)
			6-(-)-(3 <i>S</i> ,4 <i>R</i>)	7-(+)-(3 <i>R</i> ,4 <i>S</i>)		
1	Phenyl	Acetyl	6a (100)	7a (0.0)	2	90
2	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl		6b (100)	7b (0.0)	2	85
3	<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl		6c (100)	7c (0.0)	2	80
4	Phenyl	Methyl	6d (100)	7d (0.0)	2	80
5	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl		6e (100)	7e (0.0)	2	85
6	<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl		6f (100)	7f (0.0)	2	90
7	Phenyl	Phenyl	6g (100)	7g (0.0)	2	90
8	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl		6h (100)	7h (0.0)	2	80
9	<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl		6i (100)	7i (0.0)	2	90

Scheme 2. Synthesis of Schiff base derived from L-glyceraldehyde acetonide with ascorbic amine.

omer **7** was not formed. Therefore, chirality of the process depends entirely on the stereochemistry of the asymmetric center present in **5** (Scheme 3 and Table 1)^{5,6}.

Scheme 3. Microwave induced Stereoselective Synthesis of monocyclic β -lactam derived from L-(*S*)-Glyceraldehyde Acetonide Schiff base.

This chiral β -lactam **6** has opposite absolute stereochemistry at the C-3, C-4 and C-5 centers than the β -lactams ob-

tained from 1:2, 5:6-di-O-isopropylidene D-mannitol. On the basis of this study, preparation of several optically active β -lactams is possible using microwave-induced cycloaddition reaction of imines with acid chlorides. These chiral β -lactams are important starting compounds for the preparation of diverse heterocyclic compounds. These products would certainly facilitate our and others research in this area of current investigation.

Experimental

In a 125 mL Erlenmeyer flask, dichloroethane (2 mL) was added to the imine **5** (1 mmol). To the reaction mixture N-methylmorpholine (3 mmol) and acid chloride (1.5 mmol) were then added and the reaction mixture was irradiated in a domestic microwave oven for 2 min at low power level. After being cooled to room temperature, the reaction mixture was washed with aqueous hydrochloric acid (5%, 2 mL), aqueous sodium bicarbonate (5%, 2 mL) and brine (2 mL). The organic extracts were then evaporated and passed through a short column of silica gel (5 g) using ethyl acetate and hexanes (20:80) as the solvent to afford the pure product **6**.

Conclusions

Optically active β -lactams with defined absolute stereochemistry is prepared by an expeditious route through microwave-induced reaction as one of the key steps. Products are highly functionalized and therefore a number of chemical alterations are possible for the preparation of crucial molecules in optically active forms. This study produces the enantiomeric forms of the β -lactams that are prepared from D-mannitol derivatives. It is crucial to obtain all possible isomers in optically active forms for biological studies of the

products. Enantiomers differ in medicinal activities. To have appropriate chemical, biological and pharmacological knowledge, it is important to have the availability of all enantiomeric forms of organic compounds.

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References

1. (a) K. M. Papp-Wallace, A. Endimiani, M. A. Taracila and R. A. Bonomo, *Antimicrob. Agents Ch.*, 2011, **55**, 4943; (b) A. L. Demain and S. Sanchez, *J. Antibiot.*, 2009, **62**, 5; (c) S. M. Drawz and R. A. Bonomo, *Clin. Microbiol. Rev.*, 2010, **23**, 160; (d) D. M. Livermore, *J. Antimicrob. Chemother.*, 2001, **47**, 247.
2. (a) C. Palomo, J. M. Aizpurua, A. Mielgo and A. Linden, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1996, **61**, 9186; (b) P. M. Chincholkara, V. G. Puranik and A. R. A. S. Deshmukh, *Tetrahedron*, 2007, **63**, 9179; (c) G. S. Singh and S. Sudheesh, *ARKIVOC*, 2014, 337.
3. (a) C. Hubschwerlen and G. Schmid, *Helvetica*, 1983, **66**, 2206; (b) P. Areces, E. Carrasco, M. E. Light, M. Santos and J. Plumet, *Synlett*, 2007, **20**, 3180; (c) C. Niu, T. Pettersson and M. J. Miller, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1996, **61**, 1014.
4. D. R. Wagle, C. Garai, J. Chiang, M. G. Monteleone, B. E. Kurys, T. W. Strohmeyer, V. R. Hegde, M. S. Manhas and A. K. Bose, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1988, **53**, 4227.
5. (a) I. Banik, F. F. Becker and B. K. Banik, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2003, **46**, 12; (b) B. K. Banik, *Curr. Med. Chem.*, 2004, **12**; (c) B. K. Banik, I. Banik and F. F. Becker, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2005, **13**, 3611; (d) B. K. Banik and F. F. Becker, *Mol. Med. Rep.*, 2010, **3**, 315; (e) B. K. Banik, I. Banik and F. F. Becker, *Topics in Heterocyclic Chemistry*, 2010, **22**, 349; (f) B. K. Banik, *International Innovation*, 2011, 50; (g) B. K. Banik and F. F. Becker, *Mol. Med. Rep.*, 2010, **3**, 315.
6. (a) B. K. Banik, I. Banik and F. F. Becker, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2010, **45**, 846; (b) B. K. Banik, S. Samajdar and F. F. Becker, *Mol. Med. Rep.*, 2010, **3**, 319.

